

Understanding and Supporting student's collaboration and communication in blended learning

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Abstract

The report discusses the subject of student's collaboration, communication and blended learning. The purpose of the report is to describe the extent of skills that students need to acquire in the field of collaboration and communication in blended learning and the use of Moodle virtual learning environment. For this purpose, the following questions are presented and analysed in Materials and Methods: Communication and collaboration as part of Digital communication; Benefits of Collaboration Software; What is mean to be Collaborative. In the Discussion and Results section are analysed Moodle activities for the development of Communication and collaboration skills in blended learning and Moodle's Plugins to create an environment for communication and cooperation. Conclusions are drawn on the application of the various blended learning tools and the learning outcomes that can be achieved.

Keywords: Collaboration and communication, blended learning, Moodle, Moodle plugins.

1. Introduction

The theme of Collaboration and communication is really significant for the 21st century when Internet and Information Technology have entered into all public ranges and in education particularly. It becomes even more challenging to train and educate young people, mainly students, with the adoption of the Digital Competence Framework of EU (Dig Comp 2.1). That obliges us to consider our training to provide students with the necessary knowledge and skills in the five areas covered by Dig Comp: *Information and data literacy; Communication and collaboration; Digital content creation; Safety; Problem solving.*

The report analysed the opportunities that are offered to the students of Techniques and Technology Faculties -Yambol, in the area of Communication and collaboration in Blended learning.

The article aim is to describe the extent of skills that students need to acquire in the field of collaboration and communication in blended learning and the use of Moodle virtual learning environment.

2. Materials and methods

In order to achieve the goals set, the scientific report provides an overview of literary sources that address and analyse the topic. The sources used are both publications and reports of EU. They are analysed on the basis of the existing theoretical perceptions and concepts. At the same time are presented and analysed the experience of working with the resources and activities of the Moodle virtual learning environment and the third-party plug-ins. Based on that analysis, conclusions are drawn on the benefits of collaboration and communication in blended learning.

2.1. Communication and collaboration as part of Digital communication

The Digital communication and collaborationskills are indispensable and very important part of student's competences studying in different university.They are critical to the development of modern society because engineering specialties are those who create the infrastructure and technologies that enable the creation and development of knowledge, enhance communication and collaboration in the 21st century.Therefore, the EC has adopted the Digital Competence Framework (EU DigComp 2.1), that is already successfully integrated into development strategies, curricula and programmes for student learners. The EU DigComp 2.1 is the set of knowledge, skills, abilities and strategies that are required when are using ICT and digital media (Ferrari, 2012; fig.1).

The definition of Digital Competence can be broken into: *learning domains; tools; competence areas; modes; purposes* (Fig. 1; Ferrari, 2012).

Figure 1. Blocks of Digital Competence definition

The skills for communication and collaboration as a part of EU DigComp 2.1 framework (Carretero et al., 2017) are:

- ✓ *Interacting through digital technologies* - interact through a range of digital technologies and to understand appropriate digital communication means for a given context;
- ✓ *Sharing through digital technologies* - share data, information and digital content with others through appropriate digital technologies;
- ✓ *Engaging in citizenship through digital technologies* - participate in society through the use of public and private digital services;
- ✓ *Collaborating through digital technologies* - using digital tools and technologies for collaborative processes, and for co-construction and co-creation of resources and knowledge;
- ✓ *Netiquette* - aware of behavioural norms and know-how while using digital technologies and interacting in digital environments. To adapt communication strategies to the specific audience and to be aware of cultural and generational diversity in digital environments;

- ✓ *Managing digital identity* - create and manage one or multiple digital identities, to be able to protect one's own reputation, to deal with the data that one produces through several digital tools, environments and services.

2.2. Benefits of Collaboration Software

The researchers believed that team work and collaboration is better than competition in education (Ibrahim, 2014; Sackstein, 2017), and some elements of friendly competition are indeed collaboration (Sackstein, 2017). In team environment learners grow; each one offers its experience and knowledge with a deficit that can be lessened by collaboration (Sackstein, 2017). The collaboration increase productivity fosters creativity and empathy or other perspectives good for product development and organizational health. Collaboration helps to build teams that are better-rounded, saves time and supports better productivity. Additionally, when you give teams a freedom to act independently, you're also building trust, creating more loyalty and retaining talent (Frary, 2017).

The collaboration is a process of teams, and the collaboration tools are meant to facilitate those communication processes, using: *Twitter, Skype, Facebook, Scoop It, Google Apps for Education (GAFE)* that offered opportunities to share and collaborate on a global scale (Coutts, 2015). There are many different forms and types of collaboration software, from video conferencing platforms to chat apps and project management tools to shared online document storage and workspaces.

The different collaboration forms that help teams to collaborate together are: *Chats & Discussions; Commenting; Sharing; Video Conferencing; Shared Tasks; Online File Storage; Working in the same document or space together; Alerts to keep team up-to-date at the same time; Mobile apps and others* (Ray, 2017).

The most common tools using for collaboration are shown on fig. 2.

Figure 2. Most common tools using for collaboration (Frary, 2017)

The ways of developing environments that prize people working together over ones that promote a winner are (Sackstein, 2017):

- ✓ *Get rid of grades* –it is better to make learning about learning and NOT about being better than our classmates or colleague;
- ✓ *Work together as a group* - allow natural problem solving to happen and teachers need these opportunities;
- ✓ *Build relationships* - give students multiple opportunities to get to know each other and trusting relationship to be build; there are much more effective collaborations when we know and trust each other.
- ✓ *Teach how to collaborate* –showing the outcomes of collaborative efforts versus individual ones;

- ✓ *Be transparent* - lean on each other for help, switch roles, share responsibility and because all of that takes practice always build time for practice.

2.3. The mean of being Collaborative

Being collaborative in practice isto share information, insights, strategies and resources across projects, organizations and sectors, leading to increased efficiency and impact that brings all the others together in practice. No single initiative or organization can make it happen alone through collaboration, working in digital development and beyond can pool theresources and expertise not only to benefit each initiative, but also to strengthen the global community. The collaboration requires time, planning and dedicating resources to look for and develop opportunities (digitalprinciples.org, 2017).

Core Tenets of collaboration are:

- ✓ *Understand how your work fits into the global development landscape* - identify others working on the same problem in other geographies, and determine if there is a community of practice. Find the technical leaders in global and regional organizations (such as World Bank, World Health Organization, etc.) who can help you disseminate your work to other teams, regions and countries;
- ✓ *Engage diverse experts* - across disciplines, countries and industries throughout the project lifecycle. Create an engagement plan to apply this expertise at all phases, and incorporate insights through feedback loops. Look for tools and approaches from other sectors, and publish your findings so they are available to other groups and countries;
- ✓ *Plan to collaborate from the beginning* - build collaborative activities into proposals, work plans, budgets and job descriptions. Identify indicators for measuring collaboration in your monitoring and evaluation plan;
- ✓ *Document work, results, processes and best practices* - Share your code with the open source community, publish documents under a Creative Commons license, and participate in digital development conferences and other forums to share lessons you have learned and to learn from other practitioners;
- ✓ *Define how your project will contribute locally* - collaboration is the first step in interoperability; define how your work can connect with local systems and whichstandards you need to adopt to make these connections. Engage with organizations that support these standards, and participate in local technical strategy groups and roundtables to ensure that you are a part of the larger whole.

3. Discussion and results

3.1. Moodle activities for development of Communication and collaboration skills in blended learning

The developments of Communication and collaboration soft skills are crucial for the new engineers and their employers, and for stakeholder perceptions of the value and relevance of engineering education (Daniels at all, 2010).The activities that can be used to develop that skills and implement them in the learning process in Moodle VLE are:

- ✓ *Chat* - allows a synchronous discussion in real time. This is a useful way to understand the different point of view of each participant in the discussion. The way of using a chat room is quite different from the asynchronous forums, which also have their place. Chat features include a number of chat management and review features.Any teacher can add a Chat to your course; Give a chat name to show what the goal is; to introduce a description of this chat and instructions for participants in the course; Schedule future chat sessions (there are four options for this: chat without any time - at any time, chat only for a certain event, at the same time each day, at the same time every week); Save for past chat

sessions options to access past chat sessions. The administration of sessions allows choosing from several existing methods in Moodle - Ajax, Normal method, Chat server daemon.

- ✓ *Forum* - tools for asynchronous communication for teaching (sharing content or for student interaction (creating content), useful for communication and successfully creation of online communication environment. Forums are well suited for students to communicate with each other as well as to co-create content. Students can write together, participate in discussions, share files and collaborate (UMass Amherst Information Technology, 2018). The forums can be different types: *Standard forum for general use; Single, simple discussion; Question and Answer forum*. These forums allow the groups to get around certain issues that are being discussed, to create general content, to publish files or to answer questions posed in the forum. Depending on the goals set by the creation of the forum, many structured activities supported by Moodle settings can be created such as: *Forum Type; Group Mode; Assign to grouping*.
- ✓ *Wiki* - a collection of web pages that anyone can add to or edit. A wiki is a collection of collaboratively authored web documents. Basically, a wiki page is a web page that everyone from one class can create together, right in the browser, without needing to know HTML. A wiki starts with one front page. Each author can add other pages to the wiki by simply creating a link to a page that doesn't exist yet. For students to collaborate in this case, students need to use the "Collaborative wiki", where students work together on a single wiki but not an individual wiki. There are several wiki formats: HTML editing using the normal text editor such as Atto; Creole - a popular wiki editing language, NWiki - a wiki editing language similar to Mediawiki.
- ✓ *Workshop* - enables peer assessment of students. Students can evaluate other participants who upload their materials using a multi-criteria assessment form. According to the settings that are being maintained, the teacher can decide whether to show or hide the identities of the students to each other when assessing.

3.2. Moodle's plug-ins to create an environment for communication and collaboration

Plugins (total 1510 to 02.08.2018) that can be integrated into MOODLE have different application areas: *Administration; Assessment; Collaboration; Communication; Content; Interface*. Collaboration plug-ins mainly refer to student group work: *Group self-selection; Group choice*. Creating groups and configuring them creates the conditions for shaping them in different ways in order to achieve the goal of collaboration.

The plugins that can be used for Communication are significantly more (MoodlePluginsatMoodle.org, 2018):

- ✓ *Message My Teacher* - allows to configure the role of "Teachers" on a course. The blog that is created shows a list of everyone with this role in exception of current user, if they are a teacher and with a link to message each one;
- ✓ *Congrea* - facilitate real time Interaction between users. Build of Education, it is designed primarily for teachers to Interact with Students. "Congrea" lets collaboration in real time through *Screen, Audio, Webcam, whiteboard, documents and media with students* during online delivery of classes and training sessions;
- ✓ *Resource notification* - allows a teacher to notify course students by internal messaging when a new resource/activity is created or modified into a course;
- ✓ *Purpose* - a new action appears in a new entry on the end of the Edit drop-down menu, available for each resource or activity, on the course page. The teacher can control who to send the message to. The notification meets the restrictions on access to the resources of the individual courses.

- ✓ *Facetoface* -A useful plug-in for blended learning environments through which the administrators are looking for a way to manage events if pre-enrollment is required. *Face-to-face* activities are used to keep track of classroom trainings. Each activity is available in one or more identical sessions. A reminders message is sent to the users of their managers a few days before the session is scheduled to start. Confirmation messages are sent when users sign-up for a session or cancel.
- ✓ *MoodleMobile&MoodleMobileTextMessages* - The plug-in allows you to send a message to any of your existing contact groups, allowing a large number of people to connect at the same time. Without current monthly costs and only with a small setup fee to activate via Janet txt profile, MoodleMobile is a great way to integrate text messages into the university.
- ✓ *Reservation* -The main objectives of this module are scheduling laboratory sessions and exams, but any events can be plan. The teacher can determine the number of seats available for the event, the date of the event, the start and end dates of the reservation. Students can book and unbook a seat and add a note for this reservation. Reservations may be linked to another event so that students can only book one of these. It is allowed to make a reservation via a CSV file from managers and administrators.
- ✓ *CourseContactsBlock* - shows a list of course users, different methods of communicating with them, and their current activity status. By default, the block will show teachers on the course, but this can be changed as desired; the block can provide quick links to an email, message or phone to each user.
- ✓ *BigBlueButtonBN* - open source web conferencing system for online learning. The aim of the project is to enable instructors to conduct online classes, virtual office hours, and group collaboration with remote students. BigBlueButton supports real-time sharing of slides (including whiteboard), audio, video, chat, emoticons, windows, and screen. It also records all content for later playback. There are a number of settings that make the plug-in convenient for students and teachers.

4. Conclusions

Moodle supports student collaboration through all collective forms of communication and collaboration applied in different variants:

- ✓ changing the roles of "teacher" - "student" depending on the goals we want to achieve;
- ✓ the teacher assesses the participation of the participants in the course and their participation in the collective forms of work;
- ✓ Moodle offered various formats for collective activities that allow innovative approaches to their implementation;
- ✓ the plug-ins are valuable for enhancing the effectiveness of communications, which in most cases are a prerequisite for blended learning collaboration;
- ✓ Moodle resources and activities allow the integration of other external software products that can expand communication and collaboration capabilities.

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